

Enterprise Data Warehouse Design Considerations

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Abstract

In this Journal, the base lines for designing an Enterprise Data Warehouse (EDW) to support business analytics in the era of “big data” has been explained. The scope and challenges of building and evolving a very stable and successful EDW architecture to meet new business requirements. These include extreme integration, semi- and un-structured data sources, and petabytes of behavioral data as well as massively parallel relational databases, and then structuring the EDW to support advanced analytics.

1. Introduction

This Journal provides detailed guidance for designing and administering the necessary processes for deployment. This Journal has been written in response to a lack of specific guidance in the industry as to how the EDW needs to respond to the data analytics challenge, and what necessary design elements are needed to support these new requirements.

Scaling up an EDW to large data volumes is a challenge. For example, big data tends to get big because much of it is coming from new sources, such as websites, social media, robotics, mobile devices, and sensors. Deciding which of these are useful for Business Intelligence/Data Warehouse(BI/DW) purposes pushes BI professionals to think in new terms.

2. Business Principles

Organizational Consensus

From the outset of the data warehousing effort, there should be a consensus-building process that helps guide the planning, design and implementation process. Make every effort to gain acceptance for DWH, and minimize resistance to, the Data Warehouse. Use it and, hopefully, champion it to the rest of the company.

Data Integrity

The brass ring of data warehousing — of any business intelligence (BI) project — is a single version of the truth about organizational data. The path to this begins with achieving data integrity in your DW.

Therefore, any design for DW should begin by minimizing the chances for data replication and inconsistency. It should also promote data integration and standardization. Any reasonable methodology you choose to achieve data integrity should work, as long as you implement the methodology effectively with the end result in mind.

Implementation Efficiency

To help meet the needs of company as early as possible and minimize project costs, the DWH design should be straightforward and efficient to implement. If that design is difficult to understand or implement or doesn't meet user needs, DW project will be mired in difficulty and cost overruns almost from the start.

Opt for simplicity in your design plans and choose to the most practical extent function over beautiful form. This choice will help you stay within budgetary constraints, and it will go a long way toward providing user needs that are effective.

User Friendliness

To help achieve a user-friendly design, the DWH should leverage a common front-end across the company — based on user roles and security levels. It should also be intuitive enough to have a minimal learning curve for most users. Of course, there will be exceptions, but rule of thumb should be that even the least technical users will find the interface reasonably intuitive.

Operational Efficiency

This principle is really a corollary to the principle of implementation efficiency. Once implemented, the data warehouse should be easy to support and facilitate rapid responses to business change requests. Errors and exceptions should also be easy to remedy, and support costs should be moderate over the life of the DW. Operational efficiency can be achieved only with a DW design that is easy to implement and maintain. Again, a technically elegant solution might be beautiful, but a practical, easy-to-maintain solution can yield better results in the long run.

Scalability

This is usually a huge problem with data warehouse design. In order to resolve this, from the very onset scalability should be factored in. Consequently, platforms and tool-sets, that support data volume expansions in the future, should be chosen.

The DW can be an Enterprise DW modeled using an E/R model upon which Data Marts are built (**Bill Inmon**). Or the DW can start out as a Data Mart with a Shared Dimensional Model for follow-on Data Marts (**Ralph Kimball's**).

A data warehouse exists to serve its users — analysts and decision-makers. A data warehouse must be designed to satisfy the following requirements:

- Deliver a great user experience — user acceptance is the measure of success.
- Function without interfering with OLTP systems.
- Provide a central repository of consistent data.
- Answer complex queries quickly.
- Provide a variety of powerful analytical tools, such as OLAP and data mining.

Most successful data warehouses that meet these requirements have these common characteristics:

- Are based on a dimensional model
- Contain historical data.
- Include both detailed and summarized data.
- Consolidate disparate data from multiple sources while retaining consistency.
- Focus on a single subject, such as sales, inventory, or finance.

3. Data Warehouse Advantages

A Data Warehouse Delivers Enhanced Business Intelligence

Best advantages to using a data warehouse is that users will be able to access a large amount of information at one place for Risk analysis (reporting) and Data analysis based on the requirement. By providing data from various sources, managers and executives will no longer need to make business decisions based on limited data or their gut. In addition, “data warehouses and related BI can be applied directly to business processes including marketing segmentation, inventory management, financial management, and sales.”

A Data Warehouse Saves Time

Since business users can quickly access critical data from a number of sources — all in one place — they can rapidly make informed decisions on key initiatives. They won't waste precious time retrieving data from multiple sources.

Not only that but the business execs can query the data themselves with little or no support from IT — saving more time and more money. That means the business users won't have to wait until IT gets around to generating the reports, and those hardworking folks in IT can do what they do best — keep the business running.

A Data Warehouse Enhances Data Quality and Consistency

A data warehouse implementation includes the conversion of data from numerous source systems into a common format. Since each data from the various departments is standardized, each department will produce results that are in line with all the other departments. So you can have more confidence in the accuracy of your data. And accurate data is the basis for strong business decisions.

A Data Warehouse Provides Historical Intelligence

A data warehouse stores large amounts of historical data so you can analyze different time periods and trends in order to make future predictions. Such data typically cannot be stored in a transactional database or used to generate reports from a transactional system.

4. Enterprise Data Warehouse Architecture

The Enterprise Data Warehouse has a design scheme that makes it conform to the current and studied methodologies of data warehousing where the result is a star schema design. The traditional data warehouse design is mostly due to the work of Ralph Kimball of the Kimball Group and will be a source of concentration for the following discussion as it relates to the system architecture. The most poignant of terms introduced by Kimball is that of dimensions and fact type tables as the way that data need to be arranged for the eventual organization into data marts and reporting. Also provided is the manner in which data moves from the operational source, such as transactional databases, over to data warehouse itself.

The data itself moves through a tool known as an "ETL" which stands for Extract, Transform and Load (which itself stands for the steps taken with the data to build the data warehouse). Once the data are loaded sufficiently, the data in the appropriate tables give the users the ability to report their data as needed.

The High-level Architecture of a Data Warehouse:

Data Warehouse High Level Architecture

5. Data warehouse Design considerations

A data warehouse lies at the foundation of any business intelligence (BI) system. Given BI's importance as a decision enabler today, flaws are undesirable. For a flawless data warehouse design and process, consider the following cases during design phase.

Basing data warehouse design on current business needs and future needs, extensibility of Data warehouse

A key data warehousing best practice is to ensure that the data model is flexible. The model should be able to extract data from additional source systems. The data model should not just address the current acute needs, but also suffice when these demands grow, without redesigning the entire DW. Flexibility and extensibility are important features that you can equip your DW with. Many a times, scalability is considered only from a performance point of view. Extensibility would entail how easily can more subject areas be added and can columns be added to store excess data.

Investments in data warehouse design and process rarely bear fruit in the short term, and hence it would be inappropriate to be guided purely by current business requirements. Ideally, a three to five year information management road map of the organization should be factored in when creating the data warehouse design, paying as much attention to business strategy as to technical aspects.

Consider Meta data descriptions while creating/designing the metadata layer

While designing a data warehouse, poor design of the metadata has implications. Metadata is the integrator between data models, Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) and BI. However, the metadata layer often is created only to fit short-sighted data criteria and its documentation is haphazard.

It is necessary to add descriptions to the tables or columns at the data warehouse design stage itself. When business users reject BI reports they cannot decipher, the problem can usually be traced to poorly designed data models that lack easy-to-understand descriptions, and have inconsistent naming conventions. Prevent this by setting the appropriate metadata strategy at the data modeling stage of data warehouse design.

Importance of Data quality prior to finalization of data warehouse design

A large amount of aggregation takes place at the data mart level. The data warehouse is the source of data, and the data contained therein should be clean and accurate. If not, the output from the system is likely to show discrepancies, and the data warehouse design as well as process, is unfairly thought of as the culprit. It must be understood that discrepancies usually creep in at transactional data levels. For instance, consider a bank customer whose transaction details are captured correctly, but whose mobile number on record is incorrect. A change in the mobile number could have occurred subsequent to recording the original form. This example relates to dimensional data. In such cases, it may not be feasible to stop the data warehouse process and cleanse the data.

Develop a holistic RoI model for DW investments

The data warehousing project planning should identify the key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure aspects like revenue increase and operational ease. A major bottleneck for data warehousing is that these projects are looked upon as additional costs. They should rather be viewed as enablers to improve the top line, bottom line, and operational efficiency.

Data warehousing is considered to be an IT initiative.

Focusing on data warehouse implementation as a pure IT project can amount to diluting its essence. Ideally, the benefits of a data warehouse design and process have to be quantified; if not as monetary returns on investments, then at least in terms of growth in business (defined by key performance indicators). This growth can be viewed and measured in terms of increased usage of the BI system and efficient data management, leading to smoother operations, and increased efficiency for top-level management.

Consolidate historical data by beginning data warehousing early

As a data warehousing best practice, begin investing as soon as the organization implements complex operational systems like enterprise resource planning or customer relationship management. These systems are fertile grounds for data generation. Consolidating the data from these sources will immediately aid in establishing and maintaining good data quality. The consolidated data will fuel faster and more accurate business intelligence (BI).

Know the domain

The DW will reflect how different businesses interact and interface with each other to meet enterprise-wide objectives. To illustrate, if a bank sets out to develop a DW, banking-specific domain expertise will be needed to customize the solution.

Know the source systems well

Data warehousing is about integration. Another consideration is to find if the functional and technical nuances of the source systems interact collectively or work individually. For instance, a bank will have a core banking system, a credit card system, a PRA (purchase and resale agreement) system, and others. The method in which these systems generate data varies. Having knowledge to incorporate these variations in data warehousing is important.

This tip focuses on broad, policy-level aspects to be followed while designing a data warehouse. A must have guide for professionals involved in data warehouse design, development, and deployment.

This part deals with the finer aspects of designing a data warehouse process. Set your data warehouse design exercise on fast track by using these best practices.

Rather, active monitoring of dimensional data should be incorporated right at the data warehouse design stage. Quality control is governed by usage too, and the business could point out faults that the technology may forego; hence, the data warehouse design must provide for strong data governance processes in order to maintain clean data.

Plan and provision for ETL for future growth

In a DW, the ETL infrastructure would contain an ETL tool, servers, and database. If you choose the ETL tool that comes as part of a BI package, you may face flexibility issues. Such tools may not accommodate the source systems and additional data needs. As a data warehousing best practice, take the effort to evaluate and buy an appropriate ETL tool.

Underestimating the value of ad hoc querying and self-service BI (canned reports)

A self-service BI can simplify the task by relying on the metadata layer to generate the reports, without affecting the sanctity of the underlying data model. For example, to produce a report on top-performing branches, the user simply selects hierarchical columns with the titles “region,” “branch,” “number of customers” and “relationship packages.” Thus, incorporation of a self-service or ad hoc query layer in the data warehouse process can help you gain user acceptance.

Preferring visual appeal to speed

Indeed, in the course of data warehouse implementation, IT teams have noted that speedy response time in report generation is of prime importance for the BI system to gain popularity among users. To give a comparison, if a simple report takes a couple of seconds to load, the chart may take three minutes. Speed (Optimization) should therefore be given priority over visual appeal when designing data warehouse process.

Ensure that the project team has sufficient knowledge of BI

Generally, data warehousing projects are undertaken when organizations plan to deploy business intelligence. From this context, it becomes necessary to evaluate how business is conducted. Such evaluation will form as the foundation of any conversation on developing a data warehouse. The team that works on the DW development, should, therefore, have a fair understanding of business intelligence.

6. Data Warehousing Best Practices

Below are the Data warehouse best practices to be considered during Data Model design and implementation of a Data Warehouse Project:

- Data model should be appropriate (Dimensional, De-normalized).
- Consider volume of data/size to be processed during design of the application.
- Data validation should be considered as must.
- Implement Operation Data Store (ODS).
- Consider partitioning large fact tables.
- Consider confirmed facts/dimensions.
- Build clustered index on the date key of the fact table.
- Design dimension tables appropriately.
- Determine dimensions, facts.
- Determine which dim will be shared- confirmed dim.
- Determine which facts will be shared- confirmed facts.

- Plan for using parallel loading & indexing on the tables.
- ETL design should be generic in sense need to parameterize for various data sources.
- Write effective queries for partition elimination (usage of Where clauses) instead of full refresh).
- Use Sliding Window technique to maintain data — roll up.
- Efficiently load the initial data.
- Efficiently delete old data.
- Manage Batch statistics automatically.
- Consider efficient backup strategies.
- Design considering the De-normalized data for faster accessing the data.
- Use Load criteria (Drop and Create) for fact table.
- Load Dimensions on prior/followed by Fact tables Load.
- Optimize the query to fetch the data during data analysis as part of Reporting.
- Data is secured and should be available for DSS for reporting.

7. Successful Data Release Management Strategies

In addition to best practices, organizations can implement the following strategies to improve Data Release management in Data warehouse projects:

- **Release Management:** The ETL version control approach that will be used; including version control within the tool itself.
- **Environments:** How the ETL environment will be physically deployed in development, testing and production. This will generally be covered in the Solution Architecture.
- **Failover and Recovery:** the strategy for handling load failures. This will include recommendations on whether milestone points and staging will not be required for restarts.
- **Error Handling:** proposed standards for error trapping of jobs. This should be at a standards level, with detail of the design covered explicitly in a separate section of the physical design.
- **Process Reporting:** status and row counts of jobs should be retrieved for accurate process reporting.
- **Notification:** Identification is the manner in which information about successful and unsuccessful runs is delivered to the administrator and relevant stakeholders.
- **Parameter Management:** the ability to manage job parameters across environments so that components can be delivered and run without requiring any modifications.

- **Optimization:** Standards for improving performance such as parallelism or hash files. The more detailed design aspects of this approach is a separate section of the physical design.
- **Reusability:** Standards around simplified design and use of shared components.
- **Metadata Management:** Standards around metadata management as they apply to the ETL design.
- **Naming Conventions** that will be used across the ETL integration environment.

8. Conclusion

Information management is a discipline that governs accountability for the structure and design, storage, movement, security, quality, delivery, and usage of information required for management and business intelligence purposes.

Enterprise data warehouse standards, best practices, and a data management plan are critical to ensure effective and efficient storage, movement, and delivery of information. Data Warehouse Design plays an important role in a typical Data warehouse Project.

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